

ISic3452

Epitaph for Phronimos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Territory of Mineo, probably contrada Favarotta (37.307741,
14.710805)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5198

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 38 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 10 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 80-85 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not measure mm

Text

1. Φρονιμε
2. χρηστέ
3. χάρε

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Farewell, worthy Phronimos

Translation (it)

O beato Phronimos, salve

Commentary

Note that there is a second, separate text (ISic3453 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3453>]) on the reverse.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644928

EDCS 70900744

Bibliography

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 109 no.10a

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